

MICROCLIMATE PARAMETERS OF THE AIRSPACE AT THE MINSK ARENA

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***Abstract:** The proposed physical-mathematical model of mass and heat transport processes in ice rink arenas. Information about the formation of the temperature regime of airspace and the ground under the ice slab was obtained on the basis of system analysis.*

***Key words:** Minsk-Arena, Ice Rink, Numerical Simulation, CFD*

Intoduction

"Minsk-arena" is one of the largest ice rinks in Europe. "Minsk-arena" – a unique complex of multifunctionality, complexity, technical performance, equipment and facilities. A mathematical model was created for the internal airspace of the multidisciplinary cultural and sports complex "Minsk-arena" in Minsk and was used to identify parameters of temperature and speed of the internal air, and the comparison of the simulation results with the experimental results.

The study of heat and mass transfer processes

The study of transfer processes in the complex system consisting of barriers, air space, ice plate, construction elements and technological equipment is conducted by solving three-dimensional system of differential equations of motion, and convection, radiative heat transfer (the discrete ordinates radiation model) and thermal conductivity. In mechanical ventilation, the movement of air is turbulent. To account for the turbulent nature of airflow was used k- ϵ turbulence model.

The problem was solved by the establishment in view of the uncertainty of the initial conditions. Thus, these solutions describe the stationary regime of the object. The boundary conditions were determined in accordance with the nature of real physical processes. For example, on the surfaces of solid bodies, washed by the flow of air, asked the condition of adhesion. For the equation of heat transfer was used boundary conditions of the first, second, third or fourth kind.

Object, ventilation and air-conditioning systems description

The building of the ice arena has the shape of pucks, the diameter of which outer ring is approximately 128 m, and the ice arena hall 116 m. In the center of the arena, located hockey rink of international standard 60x30 m. The area of ice field is 1740 m². Building height is 33 m. Ice playground has a fence height of 2.2 m along the long side of the rink and a height of 3.2 m along the short side. Around the perimeter of the ice rink located spectator stands at 15,000 seats.

Several systems of ventilation and air-conditioning work on the ice arena. The list of these systems is given in table 1 and Fig. 1.

The computational domain (shown in Fig. 1) comprises part of the inner space of the ice rink. Part is a quarter of the volume of the ice arena and obtained by cutting off from the internal space of the rink by the planes $x = 0$ m (symmetry plane) and $y = 0$ m (symmetry plane). The height of the computational domain (from the ice surface to the bottom cover) is 33 m. The Length along the x-axis is equal to 58 m.

Table 1. Ventilation and air conditioning of the hall ice arena.

Air supply system		Exhaust system	
System	Service area	System	Service area
AA	The air supply under the seats of the audience in the middle tier of the stands	EAB	The exhaust air from the upper zone at the perimeter of the room
AB	The air supply under the seats of the spectators on the upper tier of the stands		
AP	The air supply to the ice field	EAP	The exhaust air from the lower zone (from the floor) around the perimeter of the ice rink
AL	The air supply to upper zone	EAL	The exhaust air from the upper zone

The air conditioning AP serves an area of over ice field and delivers a concentrated air jets directed vertically downward to the ice, or at an angle toward the audience. As diffusers for the ice fields taken AIR France JS DER 21 with a flow rate of 2500 m³/h (total flow 80 000 m³/h). Air diffusers situated at altitude 26 m. In the estimated region are located eight of the diffusers. The supply air temperature according to the design data set at 15 °C. The exhaust system EAP is located under the floor of the first floor on the perimeter of the ice rink and removes air from the lower zone in an amount corresponding to the consumption of the AP system.

Figure 1. Top view and side view of the computational region with the placement of lighting fixtures, ventilation grilles, working areas of ventilation and air-conditioning. (White arrows show the direction of air supply into the room, grey arrows the direction of the exhaust air

from the room).

Space for spectators is served by a separate air-conditioning systems AA and AB. Small decorative fences are located under the seats for the audience. The air flow is evenly distributed along the seats, with a total flow rate of 100 000 m³/h in the computational domain. The supply air temperature set at 18 °C. The exhaust system EAB located above the stands on the perimeter of the arena. It removes the air from the upper zone in amount corresponding to the amount of systems AA and AB.

AL supply system and the exhaust system EAL are located in the upper area of the ceiling at a height of 29.5 m and is designed to cool the ceiling surface due to possible heating it with the heat produced by the lighting system. As air distributors taken louver grille with a total air flow of 20,000 m³/h. In the calculation area are 10 diffusers. The supply air temperature set at 12°C.

In the computational domain is placed 3,750 seats for spectators. Heat dissipation from the audience were not considered due to the lack of spectators at the time of the experiment and for the possibility of comparison of simulation results with the experimental results.

The surface temperature of the ice is set equal -3,4°C corresponding to the temperature of the ice at the time of the experiment.

To cover accepted normative thermal resistance equal to 6 m²•K/W. The outside air temperature is taken equal to 26 °C in accordance with external conditions in the experiment.

The floodlights of the Philips ArenaVision MVF403 used to illuminate the arena In accordance with the project . In the spotlight is placed one lamp metal halide MASTER MHN-LA with a power of 1000W or 2000W. The lamps are presented in the form of cylinders (Fig. 1). The computational model considers the mode of maximum illumination, when all lamps are working.

Simulation result

The simulation results shown in Fig. 2-4. Figure 2 shows the flow lines of the air flow supplied to the system AP. As can be seen from Fig. 2 supply air from the air distribution system AP lowered to a height of ≈3-7m from the surface of the ice, which can also be observed in Fig. 3 and 4 (left, velocity distribution). The impact of supply air jets on the ice is not observed.

In figures 3 and 4 (right, temperature distribution), you can see that inside the hall ice arena formed by two temperature zones: the first zone above the ice surface (0 to 3 m room height), the second area on the audience's seats (from 5 to 25 m in height).

Figure 2. The flow lines of the air flow supplied to the system AP. The color scale shows the change in the flow rate of air (m/s) along the length of the streamlines.

Figure 3. The change in the air velocity v (m/s) and air temperature (t , °C) at the height of the room in the plane passing through the diffuser system AP. The color scale shows the change in the flow rate of air (left) from 0 to 0.5 m/s and air temperature (right) -4 to +20 °C.

Figure 4. The change in the air velocity v (m/s) and air temperature (t , °C) over the ice area at the height of the room, passing through the air distribution system of the AP.

Together with the study of air flow analyses were made of the temperature distribution on the surface of the ice. Design and technological parameters of the ice slab was taken according to the project documentation (see Fig. 5).

Figure 5. The temperature distribution in the design of the base of the ice slab and on the surface of the ice.

The results of experimental visualization of air flow

The purpose of the visualization of air flow was the verification of mathematical models of real physical processes and to determine whether the influence of the inlet jets on the ice quality. Visualization of air flow were made using smoke specifically designed for use during commissioning of ventilation systems. Lighting was included in the regime of the TV shooting. For visualization of air flows from the diffusers was chosen the supply system AP, which serves the area over the ice field. Smoke flow of intake air produced by the collaborative work of supply and exhaust systems serving a spectacular ice arena: AP, AL, EAL, AA, AB, EAB, EAP.

Further, in Fig. 6 shows the results of the visualization of air streams from the AP system.

**Figure 6. View from the ice surface.
Operate supply and exhaust system: AP, AL, EAL, AA, AB, EAB, EAP.**

The air flow from the air distribution system AP lowered to a height ≈ 8 m from the ice field. The result of the exhaust of the EAP system, which removes air from the

lower zone at floor level around the ice field, thereby increasing the length of the jet from the air distribution system AP.

Summary:

The mathematical model of internal air space of the multidisciplinary cultural and sports complex "Minsk-arena", located in Minsk, on the basis of the whole complex of the actual and calculated results adequately reflects the temperature and speed regime of the air environment of the hall of the arena. The obtained results of measurement of air parameters and calculated values of mathematical model are in good agreement among themselves.

The direct influence of inlet streams on the ice surface and as a result the deterioration is not marked.

Design solution the design process plate cooling mksk "Minsk-arena" provides the required temperature of ice and the temperature unevenness (inhomogeneity) of the ice surface (maximum of 0.5 °C) in accordance with the requirements of the IIHF and the relevant regulations.

The presence of zones of increased temperature (up to 1.4°C) on the border of the ice field along the sides, the width of which is ≈ 5 cm, which does not have an appreciable effect on the temperature of ice outside this region.

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